

**Multi-Mode Feedback in Large
Writing Classrooms at Antonine
University (Beirut, Lebanon)
Presented by Nina Kang**

Multi-Mode Feedback in Writing Classrooms

<p>April 22, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Foundations of Assessment in Language Teaching / Principles of Metacognition</p>
<p>April 29, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Whole Class Feedback: Identifying Common Mistakes with a Focus on Grammar & Mechanics</p>
<p>May 6, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Peer Feedback: Targeted Tasks & Discussions</p>
<p>May 13, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Self Feedback: Showcasing Growth through Writing Portfolios & Projects</p>
<p>May 20, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Final Debriefing: Discussing Challenges & Best Practices</p>

Agenda, Session 2

Warm-Up & Review - 10min

Presentation w Discussion - 50min

Break - 5min

Small Group Activity (breakout room) – 30
min

Wrap up - 5min

Multi-Mode Feedback in Large Writing Classrooms

Workshop Objectives:

- Learn to identify student texts appropriate for modeling feedback on content, stylistic, and grammatical issues
- Introduce and practice using multi-mode feedback strategies
- Develop strategies aimed at helping students to construct their own criteria leading to self-corrections and other self-directed skills

Review: Basis for Whole Class Feedback

WCF: Advantages

- Can alleviate teacher's workload
- Can be used to identify & address learning gaps
- Can help to increase student learning (i.e., studies show improvement in scores and performance-based tasks)

Why Whole-Class Feedback?

Practical

Timely

Detailed

Formative

Why Whole-
Class
Feedback?
Pedagogically
sound

Explicit Teaching (as opposed
to Identifying Errors)

Responsive Questioning

Live Modelling

Dual Level
Approach: Whole
Class (in
combination with
Individual
Feedback)

WCF – targeted,
instructional,
generalizable

*Individual
Feedback* –
individualized,
catered, specific

Part 1: Basis for Peer Feedback

Discuss

- Peer feedback is a waste of class time.
- Students do not like (and do not value) peer feedback.

What is Peer Feedback?

- *Structured learning process* for students to provide *constructive feedback* to each other on their works
- *Communication process* where students *interact* with one another to *evaluate* their works

Peer Feedback: Advantages

- ◆ Raise awareness of the writing process and reinforce course-specific criteria (e.g., identifying thesis, transition words, cause & effect)

- ◆ Develop valuable skills like evaluating, reflecting, and critical thinking

- ◆ Build collaborative learning environment

- ◆ Can reduce workload for teachers

Peer Review
vs
Whole-Class
Feedback

Peer Feedback

- **Content/Genre**
 - Audience
 - Purpose
- Organization

WCF

- **Language**
- Grammar
- Mechanics

Effective Peer Feedback

Guided (teacher led & student sustained)

Structured (with focused tasks or criteria)

How? Introducing Peer Feedback

1. Take care of LOGISTICS (specific instructions on how to pair up)
2. Present clear TASKS (peer review form)
3. Provide a good EXEMPLAR (model it in class)

Best Practices

- Provide clear guidelines and require deliverables (e.g., fill out form)
- Should take place before (not after) the final version of the paper (use for revising, not editing process)
- Repeat use of peer feedback (normalize practice)
- Mix up when and who (e.g., in-class or as homework, in pairs or in small groups)
- Integrate PF tasks into grading system

Evaluative Qs

- Is the paper organized?
- Is the paper clearly written?
- Does the paragraph have a thesis? Underline it.

Best Practice, cont.

*Descriptive, not
evaluative*

Descriptive Tasks

- State the thesis of the paper in your own words in 1-2 sentence.
- Make a simple outline of the essay.
- Highlight passage(s) that you had to read more than once.

Part 2: Setting Up Peer-Feedback Tasks

Peer – assessment template

Name _____ learning task N° _____

After reading the story written by _____ the marked faces express my opinion about it.

Criteria	Good	Acceptable	Poor
My partner's text is clear and easy to read. I understood everything.			
His/ her story includes original details. I really enjoyed it.			
The text doesn't have grammar or spelling mistakes			
The words chosen to make the story are appropriate.			
The image chosen represents his/ her story properly			

DISUSSION OF STUDENT SAMPLE (B1.2), 339 words

In Lebanon everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon ,online or on campus learning ? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

There are many reasons that gives preference to on campus learning over online learning in Lebanon for university students, one of them is that on campus, everyone can attend classes because it doesn't require internet unlike online learning where internet at home is essential. According to studies, 55% of Lebanese families after the crises are under the poverty level, so students have to work and miss classes to pay university and internet bills,without mentioning electricity crises .

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

There is one reason that makes online learning better than on campus learning, is the price of petrol in Lebanon. Recently , petrol tank in Lebanon costs 500 000 L.L , so students who lives far from the university will face a real issue especially with the current economic crisis unlike online learning where students can attend classes from their homes . But this can be fixed by taking a dorm in the university so they can reach it by walking.

In conclusion , on campus learning is better than online because everyone can attend sessions,students can build communities,and they can understand more.Even though in Lebanon everything seems like there is not a promising future but students should believe that they are the true revolution and with education they can change everything.

Individual Feedback (Turnitin) *WCF

COMMA

WC

SPACE

In Lebanon everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon ,online or on campus learning? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

SPACE

Pron

WC

Missing ","

S/V

There are many reasons that gives preference to on campus learning over online learning in Lebanon for university students, one of them is that on campus, everyone can attend classes because it doesn't require internet unlike online learning where internet at home is essential. According to studies, 55% of Lebanese families after the crises are under the poverty level, so students have to work and miss classes to pay university and internet bills,without mentioning electricity crises .

CS

Cont

Article Error

Article Error

Art

Prep

USAGE

SPACE

6 minutes (127 words)

WCF, Approach 2 (with scaffolding)

Identify the grammatical errors and make necessary corrections.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 3 (focus on grammatical structures)

The following passage is a RUN-ON with multiple COMMA SPLICES. Fix the errors and rewrite the passage in 3-5 sentences.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 4 (focus on verb usage)

Identify all the verbs (including auxiliaries) in the passage. Note all the repetitions and errors (e.g., verb tense, passive voice). Try rewriting to improve the passage.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 5 (mechanics, editing)

Edit the following passage.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people by asking questions and getting answers immediately, so they can understand more. They also can **have friends** and build **relationships , wich** is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon. In online sessions, students **are sitting hours** in front of screens. They **cant** talk with **anybody , and** if they don't **understand they** just leave the meeting.

Peer Feedback, Focus on Revising Content

Peer Review is a tool for **revision** to 1) reinforce elements of paragraph/essay writing, 2) apply skills to internalize the writing process, and 3) improve their essays.

*Incorporating peer review can help save time reading first drafts.

Peer Feedback, Procedure

1. Prepare a worksheet with questions pertaining to the writing task (e.g., argumentative, narrative, descriptive writing)
2. Put students into randomly or manually setup groups
3. Collect & distribute essays (have a system ready to implement)
4. Tell students the essay is a rough draft and will not be graded so the purpose of the feedback is to provide constructive, honest answers to help their peers improve their papers
5. Instruct students that their critiques will be submitted and graded so the students feel more accountable for their feedback

Sample Worksheet

1. What style does the writer use to introduce the paper?
2. What is the thesis statement?
3. Where is the thesis located? Does the thesis state the writer's position?
4. What is the writer arguing for or against?
5. What support (reasons) does the writer give for the thesis? State three reasons supporting the thesis.
6. Does the writer use examples or quotations to support the thesis? List three examples.
7. How does the writer conclude the essay?
8. Did the writer convince you of their position? How?
9. Name three things that you liked about this essay.
10. Give 2-3 suggestions for improving the essay.

Sample Worksheet (answers)

1. Ss use question to introduce the paper
2. On campus learning is better than online in Lebanon
3. Thesis is at the end of the first paragraph. It gives the author's position
4. Writer argues on campus learning is better
5. One reason is that everyone can have access. Reasons are 1) IT is expensive and 2) students don't have to work to pay for IT
6. No quotations. Examples are not explained
7. Summarizes main reasons but ends with a final message that doesn't really support the idea of on campus learning
8. Not really because the other side has strong views
9. Use of clear transitions, use of question at the beginning, and use of statistics
10. Provide better examples and explain

Summary Points

- There are many advantages to incorporating Peer Feedback in writing (e.g., reinforcing writing process, developing critical thinking and building collaborative learning environment).
- Peer Feedback can be especially helpful in early stages of the writing process to encourage improvement in content and organization.

Part 3: Application (Small Group Activity)

Small Group Activity

1

Break out into 2-3 groups according to level (A1 & B1.1, B1.2, B1.3).

2

Each group will be given a student sample to evaluate.

3

Brainstorm ideas on how you would structure a peer feedback task? (15min)

4

Be prepared to share 2-3 ideas with the rest of the group.